

RNA sequencing and microarray analysis are helpful techniques to detect obesity-related lncRNAs. LncRNA can alter cholesterol metabolism and can be a target for gene therapy

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Abstract- Recent study has connected obesity disorders including improper lipid, cholesterol, and glucose metabolism to lncRNAs, which may lead to obesity or type 2 diabetes. RNA sequencing and microarray analysis are helpful techniques to detect obesity-related lncRNAs. However, the important participation of several lncRNAs in controlling obesity problems is yet unexplored.

Several lncRNAs interact with and influence lipid, cholesterol, and glucose metabolism genes, proteins, and enzymes. However, the number of lncRNAs found is substantially smaller than the number of lncRNAs detailing the lipid, cholesterol, and glucose metabolic activity. This is due in part to the complexity of the action mechanism of lncRNAs and the lack of reliable methodologies to predict functional properties of lncRNA. Consequently, if technologies exist to uncover and define lncRNAs connected to obesity syndrome, it will disclose possible therapeutic goals and drive the creation of novel, very useful ways for obesity therapy. Moreover, lncRNA can alter cholesterol accumulation, synthesis, intracellular transit, and excretion. Whether lncRNAs impact cholesterol homeostasis through cholesterol esterification, deesterification, and/or absorption remained unresolved till recently. It's worth highlighting that lncRNAs have poor species conservation levels. According to a recent study, about 10% of lncRNAs are preserved between mammals and chickens and 2% between mammals and fish,106 showing that preserved lncRNAs between species may play a crucial role in modulating the metabolism of obesity in animal evolution. Despite their poor conservation between species, however, most nonconservative lncRNAs have the potential to be transformed into nucleic acid medications to treat obesity syndrome in animal studies or for therapeutic advantages.

lncRNAs play a function in food intake, associated with obesity diseases. lncRNA was revealed to have a role in HFD-induced obesity diseases, which have intergenerational characteristics. Complete decipherment of lncRNA with regard to metabolic control of obesity might open the way for precise medication and prevention of obesity transmission from generation to generation. Moreover, as indicated in this study review, lncRNA-based therapeutic approaches may minimize genetic toxicity and maybe treat obesity problems. Natural products may have a lot of promise in the treatment of obesity syndrome and additional studies are needed. Future investigation may focus on finding effective and nontoxic strategies to introduce lncRNA interference agents to obese patients via natural products and gene therapy. As a consequence, discovering a unique mechanism for influencing obesity on the expression of lncRNA might help us better understand the pathophysiology of obesity syndromes and support the design of new tools to prevent and cure obesity syndrome, especially from food.

I. INTRODUCTION

Obesity has become a global public health concern as a result of recent economic progress. Obesity is, without a doubt, the leading cause of human death and reduced quality of life in the twenty-first century. Overweight people account for around 2 billion individuals globally. 1 According to GonzalezJimenez, the World Health Organization 2 and the International Obesity Task Force have classified obesity as an epidemic. 3 Obesity and type II diabetes are both obesity disorders that entail dysregulated lipid, cholesterol, and glucose metabolism. Obesity's negative health repercussions are linked to type II diabetes as a severe risk factor. 4 According to Wilson et al.5, being overweight and/or obese was the cause of diabetes in around 21% of men and 3% of women.

lncRNAs are transcripts that are longer than 200 nucleotides but are not translated into proteins.

6 lncRNAs are classed as sense lncRNAs, antisense lncRNAs, bidirectional lncRNAs, intergenic lncRNAs, and intragenic lncRNAs based on their relative positions in the genome. 7 Signaling molecules, decoy molecules, guiding molecules, and scaffold molecules are four different categories of lncRNAs. 8 Furthermore, lncRNAs are less conserved than short noncoding RNAs like siRNAs and miRNAs, which have a complex secondary structure and can engage in a variety of biological processes. 8 The link between lncRNAs and obesity disorders, in particular, has been a hot topic of investigation.

Some reviews have recently described the lncRNAs implicated in regulating lipid-associated renal disease,⁹ adipogenesis,¹⁰ fat cell metabolism,^{11, 12} tumor metabolism,^{13, 14} and adipose tissue function in both white and brown adipose tissue (WAT) (BAT).

15 and 16 In addition, lncRNAs control hypertension and diabetes, chronic overnutrition and metainflammation^{19, 20}, and obesity-related malignancies. 21 The relationship between obesity syndromes and lncRNAs, on the other hand, has yet to be thoroughly investigated. As a result, this scientific review will summarize and discuss how lncRNAs play a role in complex obesity metabolic syndromes, such as lipid, cholesterol, and glucose metabolism, gene transcription, epigenetic modification, and the regulation of metabolism-related genes, proteins, and enzymes, as well as obesity syndrome signaling pathways. Furthermore, the current study covers the role of lncRNAs in food consumption (e.g., high-fat diet [HFD], palmitate), which is linked to obesity disorders. Meanwhile, we discuss how nanomolecules such as small interfering RNAs (siRNAs), antisense oligonucleotides (ASOs), and natural extracts (folic acid, salvianolic acid B, high stability fucoxanthin, epigallocatechin-3gallate [EGCG]) may be used to target lncRNA, which is linked to obesity syndrome, as a potential treatment for obesity syndromes.

II. LNCRNA REGULATION IN OBESITY SYNDROME RELATED METABOLISM

2.1 Lipid metabolism is regulated by lncRNA.

In most cases, proper lipid metabolism aids in the equilibrium of a variety of physiological functions. However, faulty lipid metabolism can contribute to fat accumulation, which can contribute to obesity⁷⁵, implying that lipid metabolism is linked to obesity syndromes. Furthermore, lncRNAs can alter lipid homeostasis by interacting with RNA/DNA/protein and thereby regulating lipid metabolism. 76

In the blood samples of obese people, the expression levels of lncRNAp5549, lncRNAp21015, and lncRNAp19461 were considerably lower than in normal weight people.

22 This discovery implies that the amounts of these three lncRNAs might be used as lipid metabolism indicators in obese people. During mouse brown fat cell development, 1064 lncRNAs were differently expressed on Day 0 compared to Day 8. In addition, three lncRNAs (Gm15051, Tmem189, and Cebpd) were shown to be linked to adipose commitment. 25 Researchers discovered that two upregulated lncRNAs, AK142386 and AK133540, might influence the expression of homeobox A3 (HOXA3) and acylCoA dehydrogenase family member 10 (ACAD10), respectively, impacting adipogenesis and energy metabolism in BAT and WAT, according to another study. 30 Understanding the molecular biology of brown adipocyte differentiation will require more research into the molecular and biological activities of these potential lncRNAs. WAT stores chemical energy in the form of triglycerides, whereas BAT creates heat and uses energy to guard against cold and obesity, as previously observed. 77 Adipocyte-specific metabolic-related lncRNAs, ASMER1 and ASMER2, were shown to be differently expressed in human subcutaneous WAT, controlling obesity and insulin resistance, according to some studies. 23 Furthermore, cold exposure can cause the synthesis of BAT in murine beige adipocytes, which is controlled by the elevated lncRNA 2310069B03Rik. 31 Although the lncRNA Blnc1 can create a Blnc1hnRNPUeBF2 complex to enhance adipose development and thermogenic gene expression in BAT, Blnc1 alone does not activate the heat generation program, according to prior research. 26 Furthermore, activation of Blnc1, which operates by establishing a complex with its protein partner, might enhance HFD-induced obesity. 27, 28, 29 Similarly, the lncRNA Para1 may interact with the paraspeckle component and the hnRNPlike RNA-binding protein 14 (RBM14/NCoAA) complex, controlling adipogenesis in diet-induced obese mice 'adipocytes. 29 These findings suggest that certain lncRNAs may form complexes before performing their biological tasks. 78

2.1.1 Lipid metabolism epigenetic modification mediated by lncRNA

Through epigenetic alteration, lncRNA can influence lipid metabolism. One investigation looked at DNA methylation in the skeletal muscle of Tongcheng pigs (a breed with a lot of obesity genes), lean Landrace pigs, and tiny Wuzhishan pigs, and found that multiple lncRNAs involved in DNA methylation play important roles in controlling body shape and obesity. 74 Furthermore, these lncRNAs are being investigated as prospective genes for epigenetic investigations on skeletal muscle phenotypic variation in the future. 74

2.1.2 a. lncRNA regulates genes, proteins, and enzymes involved in lipid metabolism.

lncRNA can control lipid-related genes such as CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein alpha/beta (C/EBP α), fatty acid-binding protein 4 (FABP4), peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma 2 (PPAR2), and adiponectin, which are important in the synthesis and metabolism of lipids (ADIPOQ). Notably, a recent study found that the lncRNA GM13133 partly suppressed WAT development by lowering C/EBP and PPAR expression. 32 By reducing the expression of PPAR2, FABP4, ADIPOQ, and C/EBP, Chen et al.³³ showed that lncU90926 reduced 3T3L1

adipocyte development and suppressed lipid accumulation. Furthermore, in HFD mice 'adipocytes, the translation of ADIPOQ messenger RNA (mRNA) could be inhibited by generating the ADIPOQ AS lncRNA/ADIPOQ mRNA duplex. 34 Furthermore, lncRNA can act as a carrier for protein transport and play a role in the obesity syndrome process. During 3T3L1 adipocyte development, for example, lncRNA NEAT1 controlled PPAR2 splicing by combining with serine/arginine rich splicing protein (SRp40). 35 Furthermore, RNA binding proteins have been shown to increase the stability of lncRNAs. For example, the lncRNA APOA4AS promoted the expression of apolipoprotein A4 (APOA4), a plasma lipoprotein closely linked to obesity,79 in the livers of mice with genetic obesity and patients with fatty liver disease, through an interaction with the mRNA stabilizing protein HuR. 37 A comparable laboratory investigation found that Sam68, an RNA binding protein involved in adipogenesis, enhanced the stability of the HOX antisense transcript RNA (Hotair) and accelerated adipogenesis in preadipocytes. 36 Two Sam68-regulated lncRNAs, SRlncRNA1 and SRlncRNA2, exhibited positive and negative effects on adipocyte differentiation, respectively. 36 According to the findings, inhibiting the carrier function of lncRNA might be used as a therapy for lipid-mediated obesity diseases.

lncRNA can potentially influence the activity of enzymes involved in lipid metabolism. ATGL (adipose triglyceride lipase) is a key enzyme in the hydrolysis of triglycerides. By boosting ATGL expression and free fatty acid (FFA) betaoxidation and enhancing lipid metabolism, glucose tolerance, and attenuating hepatic steatosis, the 80 lncRNA steroid receptor RNA activator (SRA) gene deletion protects against HFD-induced obesity and improves glucose tolerance39. 38

2.1.3 Cell signaling pathways linked to lipid metabolism and lncRNA

According to new data, lncRNAs can play a role in the control of lipid metabolism by acting as a regulator of the lipid metabolism signaling pathway. The lncRNAmiRNA signaling pathway, for example, is critical in lipid metabolism. According to a recent study, the lncRNA Mirt2 sponged with miR34a5p to increase USP10 expression in the liver, reducing lipid droplet formation and glucose generation. 40 In mice, lncRNA Gm15622 may be sponged with miR7423p and miR2955p, resulting in increased hepatic fat buildup. 41 lncRNA Gm12664-001, on the other hand, may be sponged with miR2955p, reducing hepatic lipid accumulation in AML12 cells. 42

Another study found that H19 decreased steroidogenic acute regulatory protein (StAR) expression and thereby affected lipid metabolism in human KGN cells, human embryonic kidney (HEK) 293 cells, and mice Leydig cells through negatively regulating the miRNA let7. 47 Endogenous H19 silencing has been shown to minimize lipid buildup in hepatocytes. 43 In another work, the lncRNA HULC suppressed miR9 production in hepatoma cells via inducing methylation of CpG islands in the miR9 promoter. To control lipid metabolism, this epigenetic change increased the expression of PPAR and activated acylCoA synthetase longchain family members, as well as their intracellular components (such as triglycerides and cholesterol). 24 Other signaling pathways, including as p38, insulin/insulinlike growth factor 1 (IGF1), cJun NH (2) terminal kinase (JNK), cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) pathways, sterol response element binding protein 1c (SREBP1c), and PPAR, are also important in lipid metabolism. Recent research found that aberrant expression of the lncRNA uc.417 inhibited the phosphorylation of p38 in mouse primary brown adipocytes, impairing adipogenesis and the thermogenic program in BAT. 44 Inhibition of p38 phosphorylation, on the other hand, has a different effect on adipogenesis. In mouse 3T3L1 preadipocytes, for example, SRA overexpression boosted adipogenesis by boosting IGF1 signaling and controlled adipocyte differentiation by suppressing JNK and p38 phosphorylation, according to another laboratory investigation. 81 Furthermore, cold temperature induced GM13133 overexpression through 3adrenergic signaling, although this expression shift had little effect on white preadipocyte proliferation. Through cAMP signaling, however, GM13133 overexpression reduced lipid accumulation, hindered white adipocyte development, and promoted WAT to BAT transition. 32 Gm16551 is strongly activated by SREBP1c and inhibits lipid production in the mouse liver, according to one research, despite the fact that SREBP1c activity is increased by lipogenesis. As a result, Gm16551 inhibits SREBP1c and lipogenesis. 45 In addition to lipid metabolism, the PPAR signaling pathway is important. 82 Three fatty liver-related lncRNAs, FLRL8, FLRL3, and FLRL17, showed a potential role in the PPAR signaling pathway through interaction with lipid metabolism proteins, including lipoprotein lipase, fatty acid binding protein 5, and fatty acid desaturase, in a nonalcoholic fatty liver disease rodent model. 2. 46 Although many signaling pathways are known to be involved in lipid metabolism, the time and spatial interacting networks among them are yet unknown and require additional investigation.

In conclusion, lncRNAs influence lipid metabolism in adipose tissue, promote epigenetic alteration of lipid-related genes, influence the expression of lipid-related genes, proteins, and enzymes, and influence lipid signaling pathways. Further study might help to validate the link between these coding and noncoding genes, as well as their possible regulatory mechanisms. Furthermore, research into the control of lipid metabolism by lncRNAs via epigenetic pathways may give fresh insights into obesity therapy from an epigenetic perspective.

2.2 lncRNA regulates cholesterol metabolism

Obesity is generally known to be caused by a malfunction in cholesterol metabolism.

83 Furthermore, a recent study highlighted the functions of lncRNAs in lipid metabolism control through modifying cholesterol and triglyceride metabolism throughout health and illness. 84 lncRNAs have a role in cholesterol metabolism, and the following table summarizes the interaction between lncRNAs, cholesterol-related genes, and bile acid (BA) metabolism.

2.2.1 lncRNA and genes, proteins, and enzymes associated with cholesterol

lncRNA control of cholesterol-related genes, proteins, and enzymes helps to maintain cholesterol homeostasis, which is maintained in part through cholesterol buildup, production, intracellular transit, and excretion.

85 According to Huang et al.⁴⁸, the lncRNA HOXC cluster antisense RNA 1 (HOXCAS1) increased homeobox C6 (HOXC6) expression in THP1 macrophages, which partially inhibited cholesterol buildup produced by oxidized low-density lipoprotein (OxLDL). However, the precise mechanism by which HOXCAS1 induces HOXC6 in cholesterol metabolism has to be elucidated. Overexpression of lncRNA DYNLRB22 has been demonstrated to increase the expression of ATP-binding cassette transporter A1 (ABCA1) and G-protein-coupled receptor 119 (GPR119) in THP1 macrophages, promoting cholesterol efflux.⁵² In addition, a recent laboratory investigation found that lncHC coupled with heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein A2/B1 (hnRNPA2B1) decreased cholesterol excretion-related genes in hepatocytes to modulate cellular cholesterol excretion.⁵⁷ Furthermore, through antagonizing the action of the miRNA let7,47, overexpression of the lncRNA H19 promoted the production of StAR and changed intracellular cholesterol transport at the posttranscriptional level, indicating that the H19/let7 axis may play a key role in cholesterol metabolism. As a result, lncRNAs may influence cholesterol buildup and efflux genes. In HepG2 cells, the expression of HMG CoA reductase (HMGCR), the rate-limiting enzyme in cholesterol production, was shown to be reduced by lncRNA AT102202.⁴⁹

2.2.2 lncRNA metabolism and BA

BA is mostly produced in the liver from cholesterol and released into bile. Furthermore, BA metabolism is important for maintaining lipid, cholesterol, glucose, and energy balance in living beings.⁸⁶ H19, lncLSTR, and MEG3 are only a few of the lncRNAs involved in BA metabolism. For example, in the liver of C57BL/6J mice, a molecular cascade involving H19 and the antiapoptotic Bcl-2 lymphoma protein 2 preserved BA homeostasis.⁵³ Another research found that H19 led to dysregulated BA metabolism and cholestatic liver fibrosis⁵¹, which might be connected to H19's role in StAR protein production.⁴⁷ Liver-enriched lncLSTR has been found to maintain lipid homeostasis by regulating the expression of the BA-producing enzyme CYP8B1.⁵⁴ MEG3, on the other hand, was discovered to interact with polypyrimidine tract-binding protein 1, promoting SHP degradation and disrupting BA homeostasis after liver damage.⁵⁵

2.2.3 Cholesterol metabolism and cell signaling networks involving lncRNA

It's worth mentioning that lncRNA and miRNA work together to maintain cholesterol balance. NEAT1 and miR140, for example, generated a unique adipogenesis-related signaling network. Furthermore, miR140 was discovered to enhance NEAT1 expression in adipocytes during adipogenesis.⁵⁶ Hu et al.⁵⁰ also found that the lncRNA RP583A20.1 suppressed nuclear factor IA (NFIA) expression in human acute monocytic leukemia macrophages via promoting hasmiR3825p expression. NFIA downregulation also reduced circulating high-density lipoprotein cholesterol while increasing low-density lipoprotein and very-low-density lipoprotein cholesterol. These investigations demonstrated that lncRNA-miRNA interaction is important for lipid metabolism, but further study is needed to determine whether laboratory findings can be applied to humans and to create innovative therapies for obesity disorders.

These findings show that lncRNA regulates cholesterol-related genes, proteins, enzymes, BA metabolism, and signaling pathways, all of which have an impact on cholesterol homeostasis. Future studies should look at whether lncRNAs control cholesterol metabolism by cholesterol esterification, deesterification, uptake, and/or synthesis, BA secretion, and/or epigenetic alteration of cholesterol-related genes.

2.3 The role of lncRNA in glucose metabolism

Glucose is a high-energy carbohydrate that serves as the primary energy source for cells in most animals, according to research.

87 To fulfill the energy demands of organisms, glucose levels are closely regulated. Because glucose plays such an important part in metabolism, metabolic problems may lead to obesity and type 2 diabetes.

2.3.1 Regulation of glucose-related transcription factors, genes, and enzymes by long noncoding RNA

lncRNAs are essential regulators of glucose metabolism, according to several laboratory investigations. Hepatic glucokinase expression was suppressed and hepatic glycogen accumulation was reduced when lncLGR was used.⁶⁵ Another study found that the lncRNA PCGEM1 acted as a coactivator in multiple metabolic pathways in prostate cancer cells, including glucose and glutamine metabolism, as well as nucleotide and fatty acid biosynthesis, alongside cMyc and androgen receptor (AR).⁵⁸ PCGEM1 might collaborate with epigenetic modifiers or histone markers to increase and maintain cMyc enrichment on glucose gene-related target chromatin. Arnes et al.⁶⁴ recently shown that the lncRNA betalnc1 was important for islet cell formation and glucose homeostasis in adult mice by coordinating the regulation of several islet cell specific transcription factors. Furthermore, lncRNA TP53TG1 was discovered to control cell proliferation and migration in U87 and LN18 cells during glucose deprivation by regulating several glucose metabolism-related genes, including glucose-regulated protein 78, lactate dehydrogenase A, and isocitrate dehydrogenase 1,⁵⁹ indicating that some lncRNAs may be regulated by external environmental factors. Notably, the mRNA-lncRNA axis is also important for glucose metabolism regulation. lncIRS2 was inhibited in a diet-induced obese rat, which was regulated by increased transcription factor MafG (MAFG) signaling, which then regulated hepatic glucose metabolism in obesity disorders.⁶⁶ This paves the way for further research into the mechanisms that regulate lncRNA expression, which is crucial in the prevention of obesity syndrome.

2.3.2 Long noncoding RNA (lncRNA) epigenetic modulation of glucose metabolism genes

Histone acetylation and DNA methylation, like lipid metabolism, influence glucose metabolism.

88 MEG3 is involved in the metabolism of lipids and glucose. MEG3 overexpression was observed to promote hepatic gluconeogenesis and suppress insulin-stimulated glycogen synthesis in the hepatocytes of mice given an HFA, according to Zhu et al.⁶⁷ MEG3 may be a potential danger factor or indication, such as in glucose or cholestatic metabolism,⁵⁵ which deserves more investigation. The lncRNA ROIT, which is linked to DNA methyltransferase 3a and then prevents the methylation of the Nkx6.1 promoter in MIN6 cells and primary islet cells, was revealed to represent a new connection between obesity and glucose dysregulation in recent research.⁶⁹ Furthermore, Yang et al.⁷⁴ showed that DNA hypermethylation elevated the lncRNA TUNAR, a homolog of human TCL1, in the skeletal muscle of lean, obese, and minitype pigs in a glucose-dependent way. Because this diseased condition also causes improper epigenetic alterations, lncRNA levels in obesity disorders might be used as a marker for aberrant glucose metabolism.

2.3.3 Glucose metabolism and cell signaling pathways involving lncRNA

Growing data suggests that lncRNAs can control a glucose metabolic cascade through a number of signaling pathways, including miRNA, mTOR, and insulin/cAMP. In osteosarcoma cells, the lncRNA PVT1 serves as a molecular sponge to suppress miR497 and enhance glucose intake.⁶⁰ A twofold negative feedback loop involving H19 and Let7 controls glucose absorption in muscle cells, according to another research.⁷⁰ Furthermore, animal studies showed that the lncRNA Gomafu enhances hepatic glucose production and gluconeogenesis by sponging miR1395p in HFD-induced obese mice⁷¹, and that MEG3 increased hepatic insulin resistance by functioning as a ceRNA of miR214 in the livers of HFD-fed and ob/ob mice.⁶⁸ Furthermore, the lncRNA ANRIL influenced glucose absorption and glucose-related gene expression in nasopharyngeal cancer via activating the mTOR signaling pathway⁶¹, which is an important regulator of glucose metabolism.⁸⁹ The lncRNA UCA1 stimulated mTOR signaling and enhanced glycolysis through activation of signal transducer and transcription activator 3 and suppression of miR143, according to recent research. In bladder cancer cells, these molecular alterations promoted the expression of hexokinase 2, an essential glycolysis mediator.⁶² lncRNAs also regulate glucose metabolism by interacting with the insulin/cAMP signaling system. Adipocyte SRA, for example, was reported to boost insulin-sensitive glucose absorption and boost phosphorylation of Akt pathways and forkhead transcription factor 1 in adipocytes (FOXO1).

Both of these activities respond to insulin and are involved in insulin signaling.⁷² Ellis et al.⁶³ found that in colorectal cancer, CRNDE increased the expression of genes linked to glucose and lipid metabolism via the insulin/IGF signaling pathway and its downstream PI3K/Akt/mTOR and Raf/MAPK signaling pathways. One research found that cAMP signaling increased 456 lncRNAs and downregulated 409 lncRNAs.⁷³ Gm13709001 and Ppargc1a are two upregulated lncRNAs that govern gluconeogenesis in primary mouse hepatocytes by regulating the expression of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor coactivator 1 and G protein-coupled receptor 155, respectively.⁷³ lncRNAs influence glucose metabolism via a variety of signaling mechanisms. However, few studies have been conducted at the animal level to further investigate the role of lncRNA/miRNA crosstalk in glucose metabolism, so more research is needed to determine the role of this crosstalk on other signaling pathways related to glucose metabolism in obesity syndromes, such as the Warburg effect.

In general, lncRNAs influence glucose metabolism, which is linked to obesity disorders. Previous research has revealed that long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs) affect glucose-related transcription factors, genes, and enzymes, as well as influencing glucose metabolism via epigenetic control and signaling pathways. However, our understanding of the relationships between different lncRNAs, as well as the interactions between lncRNAs and proteins and mRNAs in essential metabolic pathways, is still limited, and further research is needed.

III. LNCRNA INVOLVED IN FOOD INDUCED OBESITY SYNDROME

Because many meals can produce metabolic abnormalities associated with obesity syndromes, and some lncRNAs are significantly linked to obesity syndromes, the association between lncRNA and food intake has gotten a lot of attention.

There is an inextricable relationship between food consumption, lncRNA, and obesity, according to a large body of peer-reviewed scientific literature. As previously reported, elevated lncRNA MALAT1 was found in hepatocytes exposed to palmitate and in the livers of ob/ob mice, resulting in hepatic fat buildup and insulin resistance.⁹⁰ However, a recent study found that the deletion of MALAT1 had no effect on age or diet-induced adipose tissue accretion and glucose intolerance in mice⁹¹, suggesting that the discrepancy in the aforementioned studies might be due to some compensatory mechanisms worth investigating further. In addition, HFD-induced obese mice could induce a set of dysregulated lncRNAs in adipocytes, particularly lncleptin, which exhibits dynamic changes in the conditions of eating and fasting and may serve as a novel molecular marker of adipose energy status⁹², and could also increase fat mass with reduced plasma leptin by reducing the expression of lncRNA lncOb, according to recent studies.⁹³ Alternative polyadenylation sites on lncRNA transcripts, which serve as a crucial transcription factor to control body weight in HFD-exposed rats, may be implicated in HFD-induced obesity.⁹⁴

Furthermore, comparing the chow and HFD mice, a total of 124 lncRNAs and 1606 mRNAs were differently expressed in adipose tissue,⁹⁵ providing insight into the molecular underpinnings of metabolic illnesses induced by diet as well as biomarkers for the risk of obesity syndromes. It's also worth noting that HFD-induced lncRNA changes in obesity disorders might have a hereditary component. Microarray research found that 6,354 lncRNAs were substantially elevated and 7,541 lncRNAs were substantially downregulated in FOHFD mice

compared to F0NC mice when animals and their male progeny were separated into F0/F1HFD (given an HFD) and F0/F1NC (given regular chow) groups. 96 Furthermore, the levels of lncRNAs and mRNAs in F0HFD and F1HFD mice were similar, indicating that lncRNAs may play a role in obesity intergenerational inheritance. However, it is uncertain how to decipher lncRNA-encoded information in early embryos to regulate progeny obesity. Furthermore, more laboratory research is needed to establish the roles of these differentially expressed lncRNAs and their control of obesity metabolic cis and trans target genes in obese mouse offspring.

In conclusion, multiple lncRNAs associated with obesity syndromes have been found to have a substantial association with food consumption. These lncRNAs might, for example, be used to treat obesity disorders, and future research should compare lncRNA expression in parents and offspring.

IV. POTENTIAL LNCRNA-BASED OBESITY SYNDROME TREATMENT STRATEGIES

Obesity disorders can be caused by the deregulation of several lncRNAs, as previously mentioned. As a result, we propose lncRNA-based obesity syndrome therapy options, such as lncRNA interference, lncRNA-related protein inhibitors, and natural extracts, which have been utilized to prevent and treat obesity syndrome and play a role in gene silencing and protein degradation control.

lncRNA interference and lncRNA-related protein inhibitors might be effective treatments for obesity disorders. Sequence complementarity is the mechanism by which siRNAs silence lncRNAs, according to research. 97 Furthermore, siRNA encapsulated in lipid nanoparticles can be delivered efficiently and result in gene silencing to regulate systemic lipid homeostasis. 98 Rupaimoole et al.99 recently revealed that the lncRNA NRCP may be suppressed by nanoparticle-encapsulated siRNA (nanosilRNA), a therapy technique that might modulate glycolysis, similar to what was found with glucose metabolism. ASOs that attach to target RNA and inhibit its expression have also been used to treat a variety of illnesses, including obesity and glucose intolerance. 23 Targeting the lncRNA APOA1AS with short ASOs increased APOA1 expression and altered lipid metabolism in human and monkey liver cells. a hundred Antisense lncRNA might potentially be used in conjunction with a protein to stabilize the mRNA. The lncRNA APOA4AS was shown to interact with HuR and modulate the expression of APOA4, therefore modulating plasma triglyceride and total cholesterol in ob/ob mice in mice with hereditary obesity and humans with fatty liver disease. 37 Despite the fact that AS lncRNAs and lncRNA-related protein inhibitors play a key role in obesity, the interaction between them and their targets needs to be better understood.

Furthermore, through modulating the expression of lncRNAs, several natural extracts may be able to modulate obesity disorders. Folic acid [(2S) 2 [(4 [(2-amino-4-hydroxypteridin-6-yl) methyl] aminophenyl) formamido] pentanedioic acid, C19H19N7O6] supplementation, for example, was shown to alleviate obesity and regulate a set of energy metabolism related to lncRNA and mRNA, 101 protecting obesity and insulin secretion in HFD induced obese mice. 102nd Salvia miltiorrhiza (also known as red sage, Chinese sage, tan shen, or danshen, a perennial plant in the genus Salvia, highly valued for its roots in traditional Chinese medicine) may serve as a reagent for treating obesity in HFD-induced obese mice by regulating a set of lncRNAs, according to a recent study. 102 Another study found that high stability fucoxanthin (C42H58O6, a xanthophyll found as an accessory pigment in the chloroplasts of brown marine algae and most other heterokonts) could reduce the expression of lncRNAs linked to lipid droplet accumulation in human adipose-derived stem cells, inhibiting palmitic acid-induced lipid accumulation. No. 104 Green tea (produced from Camellia sinensis leaves and buds) and its primary catechin components, especially the polyphenol EGCG, have also been shown to help prevent metabolic disorders including obesity and type 2 diabetes. 105 words The expression of lncRNAs was altered in EGCG-treated HepG2 cells, according to Liu et al.49. These findings indicate that judicious application of natural extracts might aid in the treatment of obesity syndrome.

Overall, nanosilRNA and ASOs have the ability to mute and degrade lncRNAs, which might be used to treat obesity diseases. Furthermore, protein inhibitors may work against lncRNA-interacting mRNA stabilizing proteins. Natural extracts, such as those contained in green tea (C. sinensis), may also be useful in reducing the symptoms of obesity syndrome. RNA silencing, on the other hand, can only address lncRNAs that are excessively overexpressed. As a result, new approaches to targeting downregulated lncRNAs would be necessary. While RNA silencing and natural extracts are intriguing treatment options, further research is needed to determine their efficacy in obesity diseases. Complementary diagnostic approaches based on obesity-related differential lncRNA are very essential in addition to the above techniques created based on lncRNA that may be employed in the treatment of obesity syndrome. Rapid diagnosis approaches based on serum lncRNA, for example, should be investigated further in obese individuals.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Obesity syndromes, such as faulty lipid, cholesterol, and glucose metabolism, have been linked to lncRNAs in recent research, which might contribute to obesity or type 2 diabetes. RNA sequencing and microarray analysis are useful tools for identifying lncRNAs linked to obesity disorders. However, it's likely that many lncRNAs' critical involvement in the control of obesity disorders is yet undiscovered. 50-274

Several lncRNAs interact with and control genes, proteins, and enzymes involved in the metabolism of lipids, cholesterol, and glucose. The number of lncRNAs discovered, however, is much less than the number of lncRNAs that characterize the function of lipid, cholesterol, and glucose metabolism in detail. This is owing in part to the complexity of lncRNAs' mechanism of action and the absence of good methods for

predicting lncRNA functional characteristics. As a result, if technologies exist to discover and describe lncRNAs linked to obesity syndrome, it will reveal prospective therapeutic targets and encourage the development of new obesity treatment strategies, which are extremely beneficial. Furthermore, lncRNA has the ability to influence cholesterol buildup, production, intracellular transit, and excretion. The critical topic of whether lncRNAs influence cholesterol homeostasis by cholesterol esterification, deesterification, and/or absorption has remained unsolved till now. It's worth mentioning that lncRNAs have a low level of conservation among species. According to recent research, roughly 10% of lncRNAs are conserved between mammals and chickens, and 2% between mammals and fish,¹⁰⁶ implying that conserved lncRNAs between species may play a key role in controlling obesity metabolism in animal evolution. However, despite their poor conservation between species, most nonconservative lncRNAs have the potential to be converted into nucleic acid medicines for the treatment of obesity syndrome in animal studies or for therapeutic benefits.

lncRNAs play a role in food intake, which is linked to obesity disorders. Most notably, lncRNA has been found to have a role in HFD-induced obesity disorders, which have intergenerational features. The complete decipherment of lncRNA in relation to metabolic regulation of obesity might pave the way for precision therapy and the prevention of obesity transmission from generation to generation. Furthermore, as stated in this study review, lncRNA-based therapeutic techniques might reduce genetic toxicity and perhaps treat obesity disorders. It's worth noting that some research has found that natural products have a lot of potential in the treatment of obesity syndrome and that more research is needed. Future studies might concentrate on developing effective and harmless techniques for introducing lncRNA interference compounds into obese people via natural products. As a result, identifying a specific mechanism for the influence of obesity on lncRNA expression can help us better understand the pathophysiology of obesity syndromes and promote the creation of improved tools for obesity syndrome prevention and treatment, particularly from food.

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